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Table of contents

Report on industry value of infectious disease data	3
Abstract	3
What does industry value mean and how easy is it to assess?	3
Initiatives that we can learn from	4
Referencing open resources in patents as a way to assess impact in innovation	7
Patents with industry applicants that mention a COVID-19 Data Portal resource	11
Patents that mention more than one COVID-19 Data Portal resources	14
Referencing the COVID-19 Data Portal in scientific articles with industry affiliations as a way to assess recognition and usage	15
How did companies approach innovation and adapt their services and operations during the COVID-19 pandemic?	18

Infectious disease related Research Infrastructures engaging with industry during the pandemic	20
Conclusions and suggestions from the BY-COVID industry engagement task	21
References	22
ANNEX 1	23
ANNEX 2	25

Report on industry value of infectious disease data

Aims: 1) to explore the usage and value of COVID-19 data and affiliated resources by industry, 2) to demonstrate the importance of open data and research infrastructures during and beyond the COVID-19 pandemic to develop vaccines, medicines, and other industrial products, 3) to give visibility to the industrial cases that acknowledge the usage of Open Biodata Resources in COVID-19 related discoveries.

Abstract

The value of open data in innovation is very difficult to quantify, as academic research often takes many years before it reaches its full potential of becoming an invention and being produced at an industrial scale. The efforts of the public and private sectors during the COVID-19 pandemic allowed for the rapid discovery of vaccines and other products. For this study, we used quantitative (number of patents and publications) and qualitative (interviews) data to understand the impact of COVID-19 open resources on the operations of the private sector. More than 1,000 patents reference at least one of the COVID-19 Data Portal resources, and 30% of these are affiliated with a for-profit company, showcasing the importance and successful integration of open resources in the industry sector. The study also examined the most cited patents affiliated with industry, as well as identified scientific publications that reference the COVID-19 Data Portal, confirming the awareness of the open resource not only by the public sector but also by industry. Lastly, interviews were conducted to understand the impact of the pandemic on the business operations of seven life science companies, high adaptability and further usage of COVID-related products and services beyond the pandemic. Additionally, ten interviews were conducted with Research Infrastructures, highlighting the importance of time, cost, and efficiency of infrastructures' adaptability to ensure proper industry engagement during crisis calls. Overall, this study provides evidence of the importance of open data and services during the pandemic and underscores the need for preparedness, bridging the gap between public and private sectors, and continuously assessing the impact of infrastructures on innovation.

What does industry value mean and how can it be assessed?

The COVID-19 pandemic catalysed innovative responses and unprecedented collaboration among organisations, including competitors, to tackle the crisis. These innovative solutions

have significant economic and societal importance (e.g. the mRNA vaccines technology), have much broader applications and keep playing a crucial role in fighting other diseases (such as cancer).

For example, the development of mRNA vaccine technology has a history spanning many decades and has involved multiple funding sources. Critical parts of this technology were publicly funded, while the private sector built proprietary platforms, investing significant ingenuity, effort, and money. These efforts combined patents, trade secrets, and regulatory exclusivity to protect the relevant findings (Dolgin, E., 2021). It is particularly interesting to examine the analysis by Gold, E.R. (2022), which delves into the various inventions and technologies behind different COVID-19 vaccines. This analysis provides valuable insights into the innovative processes and the role of public funding in the development of these groundbreaking vaccines.

According to a study by CSIL (Florio, M. et al., 2023), pharmaceutical companies have not disclosed figures regarding their corporate R&D investments for COVID-19 vaccines, as this data is considered confidential. However, understanding the sources, amounts, and timing of funding for COVID-19 vaccines is crucial for assessing the stimulus to innovation, risk distribution, and implications for vaccine accessibility and equity. External funding for companies was pivotal in the development and manufacturing of COVID-19 vaccines, as vaccines historically have low returns and high risks, leading to underinvestment by the pharmaceutical industry. To address this issue, **public funding and financing tools helped de-risk the development process**, shifting part of the risk from private firms to the public sector and increasing returns for pharmaceutical companies. Currently, however, the [Biotechnology Innovation Organisation](#)'s trends for infectious disease therapeutics show that public financing and deal trends peaked in 2020 and 2021 but have since declined to pre-2020 levels or worse.

The challenge of assessing the full investment and costs of COVID-19 vaccines underscores the need to define the value of products in a broader context. Fiske (2023) describes the value of health data as not intrinsic to a product or service, but rather dependent on context and relationships. The **value of data is influenced by relational factors**, such as who curated it and how different actors value it. For example, the value of a dataset can be influenced by the rigour of the data curator or the difficulty of obtaining the data, and different actors may value the same dataset differently, such as in primary and secondary uses. Open life science data have a substantial impact on the venture creation process (Rothe et al., 2019). Reflecting on the COVID-19 pandemic, Fiske suggests shifting the focus from the need for 'more' data to considering data in terms of roles and uses within a suite of relationships and practices that can contribute to its value, and examining the role of health data in regulation. Also, as mentioned by Florio, M. et al. (2023), it is unlikely that the pharmaceutical industry will deploy the effort needed to prepare for future pandemics,

pointing at the EU mandate to better invest in matching public sector operations and market mechanisms, ensure proper funding, regulations, and access to the right infrastructures.

Initiatives that we can learn from

Considering Fiske's correlation of value with broader contexts and relationships, it is interesting to examine a few collaborative initiatives that took place during the COVID-19 pandemic. For instance, the **Open COVID Pledge** (OCP, Antonelli, G.A. et al. 2022) emerged to ease collaboration challenges and foster collective innovation, as top-patenting companies publicly committed to making their COVID-19 related Intellectual Property (IP) freely available. This initiative had some success in promoting collaboration and raising awareness about the importance of open science. However, its limited time, voluntary nature, and mixed impact on vaccine distribution limited its long-term effectiveness and highlighted the need for more comprehensive and binding approaches to IP sharing in global health emergencies.

Public-private partnership models have been highly effective in the pre-competitive space, boosting the research and innovation ecosystem. A prime example is the Innovative Health Initiative (IHI, formerly known as the Innovative Medicines Initiative, IMI), where projects are jointly funded by the EU and Europe's life science industries. IMI/IHI has supported [around 50 projects](#) relevant to infectious diseases, including COVID-19 and Ebola as well as antimicrobial resistance. Among other things, these projects have established pan-European networks for clinical studies on antimicrobial resistance and trials of new antimicrobials, explored effective drug delivery methods, contributed to the development of vaccines and diagnostic tests, and collected extensive bacterial data.

In April 2020, the European Bioinformatics Institute (EMBL-EBI) established the **COVID-19 Data Portal** (<https://www.covid19dataportal.org/>), part-funded by the European Commission including through the BY-COVID project. This portal aggregates databases and repositories to make high-quality SARS-CoV-2 sequence data, other molecular data on the virus and COVID-19 disease, along with analysis tools and workflows, freely available for academic and industrial usage. The COVID-19 Data Portal has been accessed by almost 900,000 users in 187 countries (last reference September 2024 based on BY-COVID Task 3.5). Building on the lessons learned from the COVID-19 Data Portal, in 2023, the Pathogens Portal (<https://www.pathogensportal.org/>) was launched by EMBL-EBI with data spanning over 200,000 pathogen species and strains, set to become a key tool for infection biology and pathogen surveillance.

There are a lot of lessons learned from the above collaborative initiatives, but the most essential is the need for continuous effort in pandemic preparedness, not only in the research sphere of new diseases but also in establishing alliances, good practices, and

agreements on licences and access to and usage of data during and beyond times of crises. COVID-19 Data Portal is a great example of how collaboration among researchers and experts in Research Infrastructures can bring remarkable results, although the value of such infrastructure resources is often underappreciated, as the focus tends to be on new research rather than sustaining existing services and creating long-term scientific practices (Lauer K.B. 2022). Examples of the contribution of Research Infrastructures in pandemic preparedness are: i) the BBMRI-ERIC ISO-related activities related to the standardisation of provenance information management and provenance data model for biological material and data for activities in life sciences, including biotechnology and biomedicine ([ISO/TS 23494-1:2023](#)) (Wittner R. (2023)); ii) The European Viral Outbreak Research Alliance ([EVORA](#)) and [ISIDORE](#), HORIZON-funded projects, where research infrastructures combine strengths to deliver comprehensive transnational access to state-of-the-art facilities, cutting-edge services, and advanced expertise, supporting scientists and industry users in their research.

Research Infrastructures make continuous efforts to assess their impact for the purpose of strategic planning, stakeholder engagement and securing funding, though the lack of systematic mechanisms to capture and evaluate outcomes poses significant challenges. Guy Cochrane, Executive Director of the Global Biodata Coalition and lead scientist of the COVID-19 Data Portal, very clearly explained in [April 2024](#) the **challenge in assessing the impact of the global biodata resource infrastructure**. As most resources are open and do not require user identification (and they should remain like this), it makes it difficult to track who is accessing the data and how it is being used. As a result, impact assessment often relies on anecdotes and impact stories, which can be supplemented with data and tool provenance information to create insightful narratives.

This study is one of the few that is going deeper into understanding the commercial usage of the open data resources related to COVID-19. Previous publications on patent analysis, such as those by Bousfield D. (2016), Falciola L. (2022), Alshrari A.S. et al. (2022), were used as a basis to build the current analysis on patents, publications and interviews. Specifically, Bousfield D. (2016) was the first to analyse the usage and citations of bioinformatics data resources in the patent literature. More recently and relevant to COVID-19, the work of Alshrari A.S. et al. (2022) examined the Patentscope and Espacenet databases, revealing that most key pharmaceutical players have patented their innovative COVID-19 vaccines across various technologies, including DNA, RNA, viral, bacterial, and protein subunit approaches. Additionally, Falciola L., and Barbieri M. (2022) explored the search criteria, main databases, websites, experimental datasets, and other resources that cover COVID-19 findings within scientific and patent literature.

Patenting activities contribute to the dissemination of novel technical solutions and innovation (Falciola, L., Barbieri, M., 2022), although according to Gold E.R. (2022) in the

case of COVID-19, patents provided relatively minor incentives compared to upfront grants and procurement contracts. Despite that, while patenting is not the only means of fostering innovation, it does provide a quantitative perspective on the activities of companies and sectors that choose to patent their work (please also see Box1: A summary of patent procedures).

Box 1: A summary of patent procedures

A patent provides legal protection and a temporary monopoly on new and unique inventions, for around 20 years from the filing date. This incentivises innovation by protecting inventors for their research and development costs and time, and they generate profit from their inventions.

The patent procedure includes:

1. **Filing**: Inventors or their legal representatives prepare a detailed patent application (description of the invention, its novelty, and its potential applications). This application is then filed with a national or regional patent office.
2. **Examination**: The patent office examines the application to ensure its patentability; this step involves a lot of communication between the patent office and the applicant for addressing issues or objections.
3. **Publication**: After several months, approximately 18 months from the filing date, the patent application is published, allowing the public to review and challenge the patentability of the invention (pending legal status).
4. **Grant**: When the patent office determines that the invention meets all the relevant criteria, the patent is granted and the inventor has exclusive rights and legal mandates (active legal status).

Based on Liu, K. et al. (2022; Supplementary Figure 5) the COVID-19 related patents covered diverse technology fields, like nucleic acid detection, bio-pharmacy, protein detection, chemical pharmacy, medical protection clothing, vaccine, disinfection, monitoring equipment, epidemic prediction, biochemical reagent, diagnostics, scanning technologies, AI analysis and diagnostic tools, ventilation technologies, virus collection and preservation methods, and other.

During the COVID-19 pandemic, vaccine developers filed patent applications to safeguard their intellectual property and secure exclusive rights to their vaccines (Alshrari, A.S. et al., 2022). Gold, E.R. (2022) observed that overall patents became more significant once the first vaccines and antivirals reach the market, by helping to improve

relevant technologies, such as better delivery of mRNA to cells, fewer side effects, and easier storage.

Referencing open resources in patents as a way to assess impact in innovation

Given the extensive patenting activity during the pandemic, it is worth exploring how many COVID-19 related inventions utilised and referenced the open resources of the COVID-19 Data Portal. For this analysis, we developed an extensive [methodology](#), and the main findings are shared below with links to supporting documents. Within the scope of this work, we did not examine the usage of individual data deposited within the different resources, we only focused on the referencing of the different resources themselves. We believe that this approach showcases the high impact of the resource in the methodology of the patent (look at [section “How did companies approach innovation and adapt their services and operations during the COVID-19 pandemic?”](#)).

The initial search for patents focused on the COVID-19 Data Portal, where only one patent references the portal as a source of “COVID-19 testing and hospital records of the UK Biobank COVID-19 Data Portal” (more information in the [Supplementary Table](#)). The fact that only one patent mentions the COVID-19 Data Portal, confirms the previously discussed challenges on evaluating the impact of an infrastructure, despite its high usage (September 2024 Task 5.2: COVID-19 Data Portal has been accessed by almost 900,000 users in 187 countries and geographical areas). Therefore we performed a deeper analysis, where we extracted the patent numbers that mentioned “COVID-19” and referenced individual databases (resources) connected via the COVID-19 Data Portal resources; hence all extracted patents are COVID-19 related. The most relevant data are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Summary of data on the patents that reference one of the COVID-19 Data Portal resources (<https://www.covid19dataportal.org/>). For more information and for the raw data see the [summary spreadsheet 1](#). All numbers were extracted and calculated in July 2024 (see [methodology](#)).

COVID-19 Data Portal resources referenced by at least one COVID-19 related patent	Patent families	Number of citations by other patents	Total number of active patents per search	Total industrial applicants per search
ArrayExpress	9	6	0	2
ChEMBL	26	42	1	10

EMDB	17	25	1	5
EMMA	2	1	0	1
ENA	13	19	1	7
Ensembl	177	232	8	47
HPA	15	14	0	8
Interpro	34	117	2	16
Metabolights	1	13	0	1
PBDE	15	33	0	3
Pride	13	45	0	2
Proteinatlas.org	10	9	0	7
Reactome.org	6	4	0	3
Uniprot.org	33	25	29	14
UniProt	841	1295	73	172
Sum (by measuring UniProt, instead of UniProt.org; see methodology)	1179	1855	86	284 (31% of total applicants are from industry)

The total number of patents that mention “COVID-19” are 23,024. Therefore, the 1,179 patents that reference at least one of the COVID-19 Data Portal open resources represent at least 5% of the total COVID-19 patents. Based on this finding, it is evident that researchers and patent officers prefer to reference the original data sources rather than an intermediate portal, like the COVID-19 data portal despite the high usage numbers of portal users. As mentioned before, in this study we only looked into the referencing of the open resources, we believe that many more patents reference the individual data deposited within these open resources.

It is important to note that from the first search in February 2023 to July 2024, there was a 50% increase in patents referencing COVID-19 Data Portal resources. While patents began to be published in 2020, the peak occurred in 2022, with a subsequent decline since then (Graph 1), but we anticipate that more patents will become public over the next year, as the patent publication process typically takes 18 months from filing.

As shown in Table 1, 86 patents that reference at least one of the COVID-19 Data Portal resources, are **active**, while the rest are discontinued, pending, or unknown (see Graph 2). The active patents show that the invention is validated and the owner has exclusive right to use and sell it. Active patents bring significant benefits to the owners such as market advantage, revenue generation, legal protection, enhanced reputation, and fostering further innovation. For more information on the active patents per search can be found in the [Supplementary Table](#).

Due to the great number of patents, it is essential to look into the most impactful patents, in order to understand the value of the invention in the broader field. Therefore, one way to assess its impact is by examining the **number of times that a patent has been cited by other patents**.

The 1,179 patents that reference one of the COVID-19 Data Portal resources have, in total, 1855 citations. By calculating the average number of citations per search, we find that the common value is around two citations per patent. The resource with the highest citation value is Metabolights, as it has only one patent but it is cited thirteen times (see Table 1 and [summary spreadsheet 1](#)).

It is worth examining the **top five cited patents** (Table 2) more closely, as they were published early in the pandemic (2020 and 2021, with only one in 2022) and most are active patents, demonstrating significant impact on other patents for several years already. Four out of the five patents have for-profit companies as applicant organisations. These for-profit companies are in the biotech and pharmaceutical sectors, and they are based in the USA (BioNTech originated from Germany). Additionally, the three are large¹ enterprises, while only the MBF Therapeutics Inc. is a small enterprise¹.

Table 2: Top 5 most cited patents that are referencing at least one of the COVID-19 Data Portal resources (full information in the excel [summary spreadsheet 1; All](#)).

¹ [OECD definition of enterprises' size](#): Micro enterprises employ fewer than 10 employees, small enterprises 10 to 49 employees, medium-sized enterprises 50 to 249 employees, large enterprises employ 250 or more people.

Search Term	Patent Title	Number of citations	Publication year	Legal status	Applicant organisation (*for-profit company)
Uniprot	Coronavirus vaccine formulations	54	2021	Active	NOVAVAX INC*
Ensembl	SPATIAL DETECTION OF SARS-COV-2 USING TEMPLATED LIGATION	53	2022	Pending	10X GENOMICS INC*
Uniprot	ALPHAHERPESVIRUS GLYCOPROTEIN D-ENCODING NUCLEIC ACID CONSTRUCTS AND METHODS	45	2020	Active	MBF THERAPEUTICS INC*
Uniprot	Stabilized Coronavirus Spike (S) Protein Immunogens and Related Vaccines	44	2020	Active	SCRIPPS RESEARCH INST
Pride +Uniprot	CORONAVIRUS VACCINES AND METHODS OF USE	39	2021	Pending	BIONTECH US INC*

The patent information also includes a reference to the country of jurisdiction. However, this is of minor importance as almost all patents are filed in the most competitive markets, such as the United States Patent and Trademark Office (USPTO), the European Patent Office (EPO), and the World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO). Therefore, in the analysis more attention was paid to the **countries of the inventors or applicants** to better understand the origin of the invention. While the overall conclusion is that most come from the USA, (the individual search information can be found in [Supplementary Table](#)), it is important to keep in mind that the USA and EU have very different cultures regarding commercialization and patenting. Duncan, M. (2022) reviewed the European Patent system during the pandemic in 2022 and proposed changes on the patent processes around publication, revoking and disclosure requirements .

Patents with industry applicants that mention a COVID-19 Data Portal resource

The **applicant's information** in the patents is a significant source of information to evaluate the usage of open resources by industry (see [methodology](#)). As shown in Table 1, 31% of the patents that reference at least one of the COVID-19 Data Portal resources have at least one applicant from industry. Graph 3 represents the distribution of industry applicants across the fifteen search terms of the open resources (more detailed information can be found in the [summary spreadsheet 1](#) and the individual searches information in [Supplementary Table](#)).

In order to understand what these for-profit companies (industry) are, more information was extracted related to the country of their headquarters, size of their enterprise (small, medium and large enterprise²), and sector of operation. The [summary spreadsheet 1: Applicants analysis](#) contains the full list of the **122 companies that are found as applicants** of 284 patents that reference at least one open resource of the COVID-19 Data Portal (as mentioned in Table 1). Overall, the main findings from this analysis are that:

- 75% of the industry applicants have headquarters based in the USA
- Only 15% of the industry applicants seem to be large enterprises, while 60% are small enterprises²
- 66% of the European based companies are small sized enterprises² (18 companies out of 27)
- Most companies are in biotech and pharmaceutical sectors (Table 3), while there have been one company in AI (Nference INC) and one in technology (Hewlett Packard).

² [OECD definition of enterprises' size](#): Micro enterprises employ fewer than 10 employees, small enterprises 10 to 49 employees, medium-sized enterprises 50 to 249 employees, large enterprises employ 250 or more people.

Table 3: Sectors of the industry applicants of the patents presented in Table 1. This categorisation is based on ChatGPT extracted information (full information can be found in the [summary excel 1: Applicants analysis](#)).

Sector	Number of industry applicants specialised in different sectors
Pharmaceuticals	59
Biotechnology	39
Genomics	9
Vaccines	6
Healthcare	4
Diagnostics	3
Technology	1
AI	1

It is common practice for inventors to have **multiple patents** on a specific topic to protect different aspects of the invention, build a strong competitive advantage, and continue innovating on this topic. In the current search, out of 122 companies found, 50% of industry applicants had more than one patent. This also highlights the importance of open resources in these inventions and their effective integration into the R&D departments of these companies. While most companies with multiple patents have 2 to 8 patents, only two companies have more than these (Table 4), indicating a potential market dominance in the COVID-19 related life sciences products.

Table 4: Top 2 companies with most patents that reference at least one of the COVID-19 Data Portal resources, and further details for these companies (information on patents can be found in [summary spreadsheet 1](#)).

Number of patents from this search	Company's name	Headquarters	Size of enterprise ³	Sector (area of expertise)
13	MAMMOTH BIOSCIENCES INC	USA	Medium	Biotechnology, Genomics (diagnostic tests using CRISPR-Cas12a and CRISPR-based therapies using its proprietary ultra-small CRISPR systems)
12	BIONTECH SE	Germany	Large	Biotechnology, Pharmaceuticals (develops and manufactures active immunotherapies for patient-specific approaches to the treatment of diseases)

³ [OECD definition of enterprises' size](#): Micro enterprises employ fewer than 10 employees, small enterprises 10 to 49 employees, medium-sized enterprises 50 to 249 employees, large enterprises employ 250 or more people.

At this point, it is important to note that this study does not include patents that, although relevant, do not reference the open resources we searched for. Therefore, applicants mentioned earlier with a low number of patents may have other relevant patents that do not reference our search terms. Additionally, **this study does not claim that the absence of the open resource would have prevented the inventions**; further analysis is needed to assess the resource's cruciality, as in most cases, the search term is mentioned as one among many other resources.

Nevertheless, it is clear that a high number of patents with industry applicants reference at least one of the COVID-19 data portal resources in their COVID-related patents, demonstrating the importance of these resources in industrial innovation during the pandemic. It is well known that the value of open datasets lies in their integration with different datasets, including proprietary data (Lauer, K., et al., 2021). Therefore, as part of this work, we also searched for **patents referencing more than one open resource** of the COVID-19 Data Portal. The combined search terms are displayed below, indicating that even if the COVID-19 data portal is not referenced directly, a combination of datasets is still essential for innovation, as previously stated by Lauer, K., et al. (2021), demonstrating the value of Open Research Infrastructures.

Patents that mention more than one COVID-19 Data Portal resources

By identifying duplicates in the long list of patents extracted from the individual search terms ([summary spreadsheet 1; Raw](#); yellow cells), we found 16 patents that came up in three different search terms and 78 in two different search terms. In the multiple search terms returns, there was six different combinations of the following open resources: UniProt, ChEMBL, Interpro, Pride, EMDB, Ensembl, ENA, PDBE, with the most popular combination being the one of Interpro, Uniprot and Ensembl.

The details of the **78 patents that reference two different COVID-19 Data Portal resources** can be found in Table 5, with the most popular combinations being the Uniprot and Ensembl.

Table 5: Summary of data on the patents that reference two different COVID-19 data portal resources. For more information and for the raw data see the [summary spreadsheet 1: All combined](#). All numbers were extracted and calculated in July 2024 (see [methodology](#)).

COVID-19 data portal resources referenced by at least <u>two</u> COVID related patent	Patent families (numbers extracted in July 2024)	Number of <u>citations</u> by other patents	Total number of <u>active</u> patents per search	Total <u>industrial</u> applicants per search
UniProt + ChEMBL	9	9	0	3
Ensembl + HPA	4	0	0	1

UniProt + PRIDE	8	44	0	1
UniProt + HPA	11	5	0	4
UniProt + ENA	2	10	1	2
UniProt + Ensembl	44	48	1	15
Sum	78	116	2	26

Although less patents are active in this search, the average citation is similar to the individual search part, on average 2 citations per patent. The most cited patent is the patent *CORONAVIRUS VACCINES AND METHODS OF USE* referencing UniProt and PRIDE (with 39 citations; see Table 2).

Overall, this analysis of patents demonstrates the significance of open resources in driving COVID-19 related innovation. The usage of open data resources is well integrated in the industrial R&D and it is referenced in patents that demonstrates their importance in supporting innovation and creation of industry value.

Referencing the COVID-19 Data Portal in scientific articles with industry affiliations as a way to assess recognition and usage

It is known that companies not only file patents, but also publish research articles, ensuring research credibility and recognition, always balancing with their strategic priorities. Therefore, for this study, we also performed a search of scientific articles that reference COVID and the COVID-19 Data Portal.

In the beginning, we made an attempt to replicate the methodology of patents in publication searches, but the reference of at least one COVID-19 Data Portal resource returned **too much data** (see [methodology](#)), making it impossible to analyse. For instance, the search terms “[COVID AND UniProt](#)” returned 9K results, while “COVID AND Uniprot.org” returned only 334 results with 21 articles having industry affiliated authors (see Table 6 for more details).

Table 6: Example of scientific articles referencing UniProt.org (one COVID-19 data portal resource), with a description of the industry affiliated top cited article (for more details see [summary spreadsheet 2](#)).

Search terms	Total articles	Total citations of these articles	Industry affiliated articles	Citations of the industry affiliated articles	Number of companies affiliated in these articles	Number of EU (and total) countries of these companies
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COVID AND UniProt.org	334	12K	21	550	23	7 (11)
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The top cited industry affiliated article is entitled “[An organoid-derived bronchioalveolar model for SARS-CoV-2 infection of human alveolar type II-like cells](#)” (156 citations; last checked in Feb 2024), and among its 20 authors three come from Single Cell Discoveries (single-cell sequencing CRO company from Netherlands). This article tested their peptide model (MS/MS spectra) “against a combined database composed of all UniProt entries taxonomy Homo Sapiens (release October 2019) and all SARS-CoV-2 protein sequences (<https://covid-19.uniprot.org/>)”.

The industry-affiliated articles constitute 7% of the total articles that reference COVID and UniProt.org. Further information on the 23 companies affiliated with these articles can be found in [summary spreadsheet 2](#). By comparing the list of these 23 companies with the list of industry applicants of patents ([summary spreadsheet 1](#)), we can identify the following companies appearing in both lists: Roche, Regeneron, Nference and Zeteo Tech. All these companies are in the biotech and pharmaceutical sector, with Nference specialising in AI models. This confirms the high integration of UniProt (one of the COVID-19 Data Portal resources) in their R&D departments, **not only for patenting purposes but also for publishing scientific articles**.

Unlike the patents, the **COVID-19 Data Portal itself is referenced in 363 articles** (more information in Table 7 and [Methodology](#)).

Table 7: Scientific articles referencing the COVID-19 data portal (for more details see [summary spreadsheet 2](#)).

Search terms	Total articles	Total citations of these articles	Industry affiliated articles	Citations of the industry affiliated articles	Number of companies affiliated in these returns	Number of EU (and total) countries of these companies
“COVID-19 data portal”	363	10K	17	745	25	4 (11)

While industry-affiliated articles constitute only 4.7% of those referencing the COVID-19 Data Portal, this indicates the presence of public-private collaborative projects. Most of these articles have multiple authors, making it common for more than one company to be affiliated with these articles. This demonstrates recognition and awareness of the portal not only by academia but also by the private sector. The full list of companies and their corresponding articles can be found in [summary spreadsheet 2](#).

By comparing the list of the 25 companies with the list of industry patent applicants ([summary spreadsheet 1](#)), we find that only two companies appear in both lists: Pfizer and Janssen (both in the pharmaceutical sector).

It is important to examine the industry-affiliated articles to understand how the COVID-19 Data Portal was used. Therefore, we examined the text of the highly cited ones (see relevant information in Table 8).

Table 8: Information on the top cited articles that mention the COVID-19 Data Portal with at least one author from industry, with a description of the article.				
Top cited articles (citations; last checked February 2023)	Affiliated company's name	Headquarters Country	Company Size⁴	Sector
The National COVID Cohort Collaborative (N3C): Rationale, design, infrastructure, and deployment (356)	Janssen	USA	Large	Pharmaceuticals
	TriNetX	USA	Medium	Healthcare Technology
	IQVIA	USA	Large	Healthcare Data and Analytics
This article has 255 authors, among which 3 companies are represented. In this article, the COVID-19 Data Portal was cited as an “international collaboration for building infrastructure for a global approach”.				
GA4GH: International policies and standards for data sharing across genomic research and healthcare (109)	Invitae	USA	Large	Genetic Testing
	PhenoTips	Canada	Small	Healthcare Technology
	AWS	USA	Large	Cloud Computing
	MyOme, Inc	USA	Small	Genetic Testing
	Kelly Government Solutions	USA	Large	Staffing and Recruitment
This article has 202 authors, among which 5 companies. This article references the COVID-19 Data Portal among others as one of the strategic alignments among others, where “GA4GH worked to ensure that the species-agnostic elements of genomic data sharing standards are transferred into the infectious disease community”.				
The IUPHAR/BPS guide to PHARMACOLOGY in 2022: curating pharmacology for COVID-19, malaria and antibacterials (105)	Spedding Research Solutions	UK	Small	Research Services (consultancy)

⁴ [OECD definition of enterprises' size](#): Micro enterprises employ fewer than 10 employees, small enterprises 10 to 49 employees, medium-sized enterprises 50 to 249 employees, large enterprises employ 250 or more people.

This is the top cited [European](#) industry affiliated article, where among its 10 authors one comes from a company. This article references the COVID-19 Data Portal “as COVID-19 trusted resources for proteins”.

By looking into the articles text of referencing the COVID-19 Data Portal, we can definitely see that the **portal is a world wide recognised initiative by the scientific community including the industry sector.**

How did companies approach innovation and adapt their services and operations during the COVID-19 pandemic?

It is well-known that many start-ups and small-to-medium-sized companies (SMEs)⁴ in the life sciences rely heavily on open data resources to operate (Lauer, K. et al., 2021). Companies continuously innovate or even pivot their strategic priorities based on market needs, which was particularly evident during the pandemic. However, this innovation is not always documented in scientific publications or patent filings, as it depends on the company's mandates or operating procedures. This makes it **challenging to continuously collect relevant information to demonstrate the impact of open resources on company development.**

For this reason, the BY-COVID project's Task 7.2 on industry engagement aimed to collect case studies describing innovative processes in industry from the beginning of the project. Nevertheless, this has proven to be a challenging task, as company representatives are not always open or allowed to share information, or they may not see the value in sharing their case studies. Additionally, individual representatives may not have the full story, especially in the case of large enterprises, or the company may have already shifted focus to another emergency topic.

To address these challenges, a combination of qualitative and quantitative information was extracted to better understand the value to industry of open data as part of this study. Collection of qualitative information was done via interviews (see [methodology](#)).

Lauer, K.B. interviewed 17 individuals (citizens, industry representatives, and academics), as part of her thesis (2022). All respondents agreed that companies should be able to exploit open data resources for free and without restrictions to enable scientific discovery and benefit society through job creation, tax contributions, or life saving medicines. However, **opinions diverged on whether the equitable sharing of public health and societal benefits** or revenues from products developed with open data resources **is appropriately addressed in a pandemic context.** One respondent stated that access to open sequencing data of the virus accelerated the repurposing of existing vaccines. Another respondent from a large pharmaceutical company argued that while basic research relies

on open resources, the costly development of products justifies the need for certain resources to not be freely available.

Some additional interviews took place in summer 2024, aiming to understand the business operations of companies during and after the COVID-19 pandemic. Seven company representatives shared their experiences across multiple questions. All of the interviewees have utilised one or more services from the Life Sciences Research Infrastructures, and all have used the Open Biodata resources that we examined in the patents mentions ([section “Referencing open resources in patents as a way to assess impact in innovation”](#)) in some of their procedures. However, most interviewees were unable to provide an opinion on the role of open data within their company's business model, as this varies per department and product/service. For this reason, we believe that the number of patents referencing the COVID-19 Data Portal resources and their data is likely higher than what was identified in this study (see relevant [section](#)). The key findings from these interviews are summarised in [Table 9; Annex 1](#).

Among the interviewees, there were representatives from both large enterprises and SMEs, representing a diversity of company sizes and sectors. The main conclusions from these interviews is that most companies didn't change their business models, the COVID related discoveries of these companies are still used or are adapted to the current needs of the market, and most are publishing data and reports on specific technological areas. Then, in terms of essential skills during the pandemic, different scientific and technical skills were mentioned, but also some pointed at soft skills like engagement with policy makers and public bodies. Regarding the question on increased funding opportunities, most seem to think that there has been more knowledge and attention on life sciences and resilient funds, though half do not find this necessarily applicable to the needs of the company.

At the end of the interviews, the question “What would you have done differently, if you were to go back to the beginning of the pandemic?” was asked, and here are the responses⁵:

- [Interviewee 1 \(Anonymous\)](#): “The collection of data initially regarding COVID was not harmonious, the existence of standard operational procedures from the beginning would have been an enormous help.”
- [Interviewee 2 \(altona Diagnostics GmbH\)](#): “We would have done the same: develop a diagnostic test and make it available to diagnostic laboratories as fast as possible.”
- [Interviewee 3 \(Anonymous\)](#): “Democratising access to data, aligning citizens and clinicians to gather info is of great importance.”

⁵ Affiliation is provided only for interviewees who consented to be identified and did not request anonymity.

- Interviewee 4 (Anonymous): “Closer collaboration with non-commercial suppliers such as EVAg and better understanding of permit compliance topics.”
- Interviewee 5 (Netcompany-Intrasoft): “Encourage open data sharing, minimise data silos, enhance timely and efficient collaboration across different stakeholders and across borders.”
- Interviewee 6 (Aplex Bio): “Smarter usage of available open-data platforms in support of method design and development. More active pursuit of validation with key stakeholders to expedite method adoption and implementation”.
- Interviewee 7 (Anonymous): “To push further to ensure a cross-sectoral coordinated response to the pandemic. There was a lack of unified vision of likely scenarios impacting the quality of the response and business resilience.”

In summary, the interviewees highlighted the **importance of standardised data collection procedures and open data sharing to prevent data silos and enhance collaboration across different stakeholders and borders**. They also emphasised the need for closer collaboration with non-commercial suppliers, better understanding of permit compliance, and a unified vision to ensure a coordinated response to pandemics, which would improve the quality of the response and business resilience. Also, the **interviewed life sciences companies seem to be overall adjustable to new market needs and raising topics**. Lastly, we understand that open data resources appear to be so well integrated into the R&D procedures of companies that their importance is taken for granted, unlike other areas where challenges are more evident.

Infectious disease related Research Infrastructures engaging with industry during the pandemic

The BY-COVID project has been a great example of a collaborative project that brings together organisations across countries. Some of these organisations worked extensively to engage with industry during the pandemic, therefore it was considered essential to also share some lessons learnt from this experience. For this, 9 ESFRI (European Strategy Forum of Research Infrastructures) Research Infrastructures and 2 infectious diseases-related networks were interviewed and the main information is gathered in [Table 10; Annex 2](#).

The interviews highlight the diverse approaches to engage with industry taken by Research Infrastructures during the pandemic, which is understandable given the variety of services they provide. Despite these differences, most interviewees confirmed that the interaction

with industry improved during the pandemic, as now there are more users, visibility and services available for industrial usage. Also, there is more funding on pandemic preparedness and collaborative projects, like ISIDORE and others. A common challenge for all the interviewed representatives has been the infrequent reference of their Research Infrastructures in research outcomes such as industry publications or patents, making it challenging to assess their impact on innovation. Some regulations seem to affect industry interactions of the Research Infrastructures like General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), Transnational Access (TNA) and fair access to products with profitability agreements. Also, a few milestones with long-term effect were mentioned like lessons learned for preparedness ([paper](#)), Vaccine Research and Development [Infrastructure](#), BBMRI [ISO/TS 23494](#) action, [Pathogens portal](#) and the [Infectious Disease Toolkit](#).

Similarly, to the industry interviews, the question “What would you have done differently, if you were to go back to the beginning of the pandemic?” was asked, and here are the responses:

- [ERINHA](#): “In hindsight, we would probably move on quicker with the establishment of a response catalogue of services, emergency procedures for the selection and implementation of services, and broad communication to user communities.”
- [EATRIS](#): “We need to ensure that we have flexible guidelines for sample, and also we need a cultural change and readiness for industry with dedicated people and organisations to provide facilities fast and efficiently”
- [TRANSVAC project](#): “Clarity of guidelines and procedures of FAIR and data preparation for new procedures for users”
- [ELIXIR](#): “Promotion of relevant data infrastructures that are fully compliant with EU rules, regulations and principles (compared to non-EU alternatives), and plans for emergency reactions of Research Infrastructures.”
- [BBMRI](#): “Deepen and accelerate collaborative frameworks with industry stakeholders.”
- [MIRRI](#): “Having a plan supporting the provision of strains as reference material”
- [ECRIN](#): “Better coordination of European efforts was needed sooner. Setting up and properly funding (permanent) infrastructures and expert networks for pandemic preparedness will be key to handling future pandemics.”
- [Euro-BioImaging](#): “Better highlight our capabilities and service offer directly applicable to infectious disease research, such as relevant data sets, remote access options or BSL3 facilities”

In summary, the interviewees emphasised the need for establishment of emergency procedures, and broad communication to user communities. They also highlighted the importance of flexible guidelines for sample handling, cultural changes to enhance industry engagement, and the promotion of data infrastructures compliant with EU regulations.

Conclusions and suggestions from the BY-COVID industry engagement task

Through the BY-COVID project and Task 7.2, diverse efforts have been made to engage with industry through surveys, events, and interviews. These activities were thoroughly described in the BY-COVID Stakeholder Engagement Report (Deliverable 6.1) and the Industry Engagement [session 4.4.2](#). However, these efforts alone did not provide a clear view of the industry value of infectious disease data during the pandemic, as what we saw is that industry representatives often do not see the return on investing their time in sharing experiences, or they may not have a full story to share. Additionally, Research Infrastructures and Open Data Resources have limited ways of assessing their impact on final industrial products, and COVID-19 research is no longer a high-level priority topic for companies. Considering these challenges, examining patents and publications that reference the COVID-19 Data Portal or its open resources was the additional method used to assess the impact of infectious disease data and the COVID-19 Data Portal on industrial innovation.

This study provides an in-depth investigation into the effect of COVID-19 related open biodata resources on industrial inventions by examining patents and publications. However, it is not mandatory for patents to mention Open Biodata Resources, and anecdotal evidence suggests that some patents may deliberately omit references to openly available data to maintain methodological secrecy. Therefore, this work can only state that at least 1173 patents have relied on at least one of the COVID-19 Data Portal resources for their inventions. Also, this study should be considered as a source of good practices of companies that mention Open Biodata resources in their inventions related to COVID-19.

Finding easily measurable indicators to assess the impact of Research Infrastructures on innovation is a crucial and difficult action that should be considered in future research strategies. Along with this, there is a need to ensure that external parties use and reference openly available resources, such as research infrastructures.

Pandemic preparedness has received significant attention post-pandemic and should serve as a motivation point for funders, policymakers, academics, and industry to engage in projects that ensure the preparation of response plans for potential crisis scenarios across various topics, not just pandemics. Additionally, it is important for organisational strategies and guidelines to include plans for diverse stakeholder engagement during moments of crisis. Overall, more investment in pre-competitive projects in the life sciences is crucial to

ensure the applicability of research outcomes across diverse domains, as crises affect many different sectors, and solutions can be found in various fields.

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ANNEX 1

Table 9: Qualitative information from seven companies was extracted through interviews to understand better their business operations during the COVID-19 pandemic. The answers to most relevant questions are shared here.

Interviewee (Company name)	Sector	Company's size ⁴	Did your company's business model change during the pandemic?	Are you patenting or publishing anything relevant?	What skills/knowledge were important in your role during the pandemic?	Do you think there is more funding in life sciences because of the pandemic?	Are any of your products developed during the pandemic still used or adapted to your current needs?
Interviewee 1 (Anonymous)	Healthcare Analytics	Medium	Yes, started with COVID and now all infectious diseases, (also for animals), cardio metabolic and neurodegenerative diseases	Yes, we produce tailored reports and answer specific requests from clients	Biomedical, data infrastructure /analysis, government public health policy	As a small company, EU funding is hard due to expectations of in-kind work, legal concerns, size requirements, and low success rate, so it is more about building a reputation than a viable opportunity	Yes
Interviewee 2 (altona Diagnostics GmbH)	Molecular Diagnostics	Medium	No, products didn't change, main focus was already emerging diseases	No patents. Yes, information on clinical performance of the products in publications.	Past experience with emerging diseases, close contact to KOLs	Not specifically, however, reimbursement, incentivised testing.	Yes, the respective PCR products are still available.

Interviewee 3 (Anonymous)	Bioinformatics	Small	No, e-health area since 2008, mobile app integration	Yes, publications as part of PCP project	NA	Yes, resilient fund as an outcome of pandemic, R&D in applied research	Yes
Interviewee 4 (Anonymous)	Pharmaceuticals	Large	No	Yes, covid oligonucleotides	Resilience, agility, virology and PCR development, close relationship with regulatory bodies.	Life Sciences value is more broadly acknowledged. More funding available during but not after.	Yes
Interviewee 5 (Netcompany-Intrasoft)	IT Solutions and Services	Large	Yes, new assets, services and products have been developed (UNIFY-DATA, My e-hospital, tender on development of HERA's ATHINA, etc.)	Yes, publications on technological and research results, contribution to HERA with relevant EU-funded projects (COVID-X, STAMINA, Eur3ka, etc.)	Bridging the needs of healthcare providers, national planners and technologies to fight the pandemic with timely, quality and accessible data solutions.	Yes, through EU4Health and HADEA calls associated with HERA, and through the Cluster3 work programme on pandemic/emerging health threats.	Yes
Interviewee 6 (Aplex Bio)	Biotechnology	Small	Company was founded when the pandemic started and it partially shaped the hpPCR business model	Yes, publication reporting the application of hpPCR to monitor COVID variants in wastewater	Agility strengthened by previous experience with multiple molecular diagnostic methods applied to other pathogens and matrices	Yes. Not only more non-dilutive funding opportunities but also a higher perceived value of molecular diagnostic tools	Yes, hpPCR kits were developed during the pandemic but can be applied for other pathogens and targets

Interviewee 7 (Anonymous)	Pharmaceuticals	Large	Increase digitalization trend and remote work habits	No specific changes compared to our routine R&D pipeline activities	Ability to understand the epidemic dynamics, likely scenarios and their impact on our business resilience.	Not anymore; “panic and neglect” scenario where money are spent when an outbreak occurs, but neglecting to fund preparedness	No
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ANNEX 2

Table 10: Qualitative information from eight ESFRI Research Infrastructures and two infectious diseases-related networks was extracted through interviews to understand better their industry engagement during the COVID-19 pandemic. The answers to most relevant questions are shared here.

Organisation's name	Sector	Type of industrial interaction	Has it been a change of interaction during the pandemic?	Are there more relevant funding opportunities?	Do companies reference the RI's usage in their products, webpage, publications or patents?	Have there been any particular regulations that affect industry interactions?	Is there any particular milestone during the pandemic that has a long-term effect on the organisation?
EVAg	Viral Resources	Regular viral material orders	Yes, double end users (most return users)	Yes	No	Yes	
<p>Question: What would you have done differently, if you were to go back to the beginning of the pandemic? Answer: –</p>							
ERINHA	Infectious Diseases (highly pathogenic agents)	Contract research, EU-funded TNA and collaboration in EU-funded	Yes, expanding the scope of the RI, scientific strategy and capacity-building strategy (e.g.	Yes, due to the political interest for pandemic preparedness, & due to the	Not always; hard to make people remember to reference	Fair access to products with agreements on profitability (great impact on global south)	Yes, the shift in our scientific strategy that impacted our recruitment strategy for new ERINHA

		projects (e.g., NAVIPP)	including BSL-3 labs.)	ISIDORE users			members (i.e. integration of BSL-3 labs.)
<p>Question: What would you have done differently, if you were to go back to the beginning of the pandemic? Answer: “In hindsight, we would probably move on quicker with the establishment of a response catalogue of services, emergency procedures for the selection and implementation of services, and broad communication to user communities.”</p>							
EATRIS	Translational Medicine	Matchmaking with letter of engagement	Yes, through the EATRIS COVID-19 forum , no fee, no NDA for more than 40 projects	Yes, e.g. Codex4SMEs and ISIDORE that ensure professional delivery	No, testimonials at the end of the project	NA	EATRIS COVID-19 forum still open and used for Long COVID, and preparedness for future (paper)
<p>Question: What would you have done differently, if you were to go back to the beginning of the pandemic? Answer: “We need to ensure that we have flexible guidelines for sample, and also we need a cultural change and readiness for industry with dedicated people and organisations to provide facilities fast and efficiently”.</p>							
TRANSVAC project	Vaccinology	Through TNA and some service providers being from industry	Yes, adapted through TRANSVAC2 and ISIDORE	Now calls for pandemic preparedness, and as part of the vaccine hub	Yes, in a few patents, and in publications, the project funding and partners are referenced.	Most relevant is the TNA basic EC guidelines	Target for Vaccine Research and Development Infrastructure
<p>Question: What would you have done differently, if you were to go back to the beginning of the pandemic? Answer: “Clarity of guidelines and procedures of FAIR and data preparation for new procedures for users”</p>							
ELIXIR	Bioinformatics	Collaborative projects, overall free/open use	No, just more exploration of the infectious disease sector	Yes for pandemic preparedness	No	Not in particular, most relevant is the GDPR	The pathogen portal and the Infectious disease Toolkit
<p>Question: What would you have done differently, if you were to go back to the beginning of the pandemic? Answer: “Promotion of relevant data infrastructures that are fully compliant with EU rules, regulations and principles (compared to non-EU alternatives), and plans for emergency reactions of Research Infrastructures.”</p>							
BBMRI	Biobanking	Requests for samples and data usage	Yes, industry had specific focus on pandemic related samples and data	Yes, due to the political interest for pandemic preparedness, & due to the ISIDORE users	No	No (regular ethical approvals and national regulations on biobanking and sample data handling)	No
<p>Question: What would you have done differently, if you were to go back to the beginning of the pandemic? Answer: “Deepen and accelerate collaborative frameworks with industry stakeholders.”</p>							

EU-OPENS CR EEN	Chemical Biology	Collaborative development projects	No, we just stated the industry engagement at this time.	EU-OPENS GREEN DRIVE allowed us to start our first projects.	No, but we go for collaborative publications.	FAIR data policies are a problem for industry. We have only a 3 year embargo on the data.	We keep having many projects in COVID and other infectious diseases even today.
Question: What would you have done differently, if you were to go back to the beginning of the pandemic? Answer: —							
MIRRI	Microbial Resources	Provider of strains and services	Increase on requests for ISO virus standards	Yes	No	N/A	N/A
Question: What would you have done differently, if you were to go back to the beginning of the pandemic? Answer: <i>“Having a plan supporting the provision of strains as reference material”</i>							
Instruct	Structural Biology	Collaborative development and projects (ie: vaccine develop), & Industry users	More visibility via projects such as ISIDORE with new users, also from industries/SMEs	Yes, via ISIDORE	No, but we go for collaborative publications (eg: doi.org/10.1038/ s41467-020-203 21-x)	NA	Increase infectious disease users.
Question: What would you have done differently, if you were to go back to the beginning of the pandemic? Answer: —							
Euro-BioIm aging	Imaging and Image Data Services	Collaborative projects, fee-for-servi ce access	Focus on remote access and data services, but not restricted to industry	Yes, for pandemic preparedne ss and infectious disease research	Not applicable, as we did not have company users with projects related to Covid-19	Not pandemic-spe cific, a focus is on GDPR and data security for remote access	BY-COVID and ISIDORE projects, remote access provision and the inclusion of imaging facilities with higher BSL increased our expertise. And our data stewardship service increases FAIR data that benefits industry partners too.
Question: What would you have done differently, if you were to go back to the beginning of the pandemic? Answer: <i>“Better highlight our capabilities and service offer directly applicable to infectious disease research, such as relevant data sets, remote access options or BSL3 facilities”</i>							
	Clinical Research	Through collaborative projects for	No	Yes, ISIDORE, ECRAID,	Publications on SME-initiated trials often	Not in particular, most relevant is the GDPR	Still working on pandemic preparedness/ infectious

ECRIN		SME-led clinical studies.		ERA4HEALTH.	ECRIN services are acknowledged		diseases. Also funding for developing disease-agnostic tools and methodologies.
<p><u>Question:</u> What would you have done differently, if you were to go back to the beginning of the pandemic?</p> <p><u>Answer:</u> <i>“Better coordination of European efforts was needed sooner. Setting up and properly funding (permanent) infrastructures and expert networks for pandemic preparedness will be key to handling future pandemics.”</i></p>							

